

ANALYSIS OF DEFORMATION AND FAILURE OF POLYMER-BONDED EXPLOSIVES USING COUPLED PLASTIC DAMAGE MODEL

Xicheng Huang^{*1,2}, Chengjun Chen^{1,2}, Gang Chen^{1,2}, Ming Liu^{1,2}

¹ *Institute of Systems Engineering, China Academy of Engineering Physics, CHINA*
PO Box 919-401, Mianyang, Sichuan, 621900
Email: huangxc@caep.cn

² *Software Center for High Performance Numerical Simulation, CAEP, Beijing, China*

Keywords: coupled plastic damage, dynamic constitutive model, failure, polymer-bonded explosive, Steven test

ABSTRACT

In order to reveal the deformation characteristics of PBX under complex stress states and various strain rates, the material constitutive model is employed in this study based on the damaged plasticity model proposed by Lee and Fenves. The model, which is derived from a generalization of classical plasticity theory and isotropic damage theory of Kachanov, couples plasticity and damage, and is thermodynamically consistent. The yield condition uses the yield function proposed by Lubliner et al. and incorporates the modifications proposed by Lee and Fenves to account for different evolution of strength under tension and compression. The flow potential function is the Drucker-Prager hyperbolic function, and the non-associated potential flow is also assumed. The damage variable, defined as a scalar degradation of material stiffness, is computed from two independent uniaxial damage variables, and weighted by functions of the stress state. For the complex stress state and complex loading path, the scalar degradation variable is consistent with the uniaxial monotonic responses, and captures the complexity associated with the degradation mechanisms. The Steven impact test on PBX is simulated by use of the plastic-damage model, and the ignition threshold for PBX under low velocity impact is discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymer-bonded explosives (PBXs), highly particle filled composite materials comprised of 90–95% by weight of powerful secondary explosive crystals held together by a polymeric binder (5–10% by weight), have been used in a wide variety of applications ranging from rocket propellants to the main explosive charge in conventional munitions for civil and defense fields. Many interesting problems associated with PBXs have been attracting researchers in the fields of solid mechanics and chemistry. For instance, the complex mechanical behaviors, including coupled plastic damage of PBXs, have been a subject of interest to both design engineers and technological development researchers. This is concerned with the safety of explosives under low velocity impact. Understanding and modeling the mechanical response of polymer-based composites is of great interest for defense and commercial applications related to (1) the need for predictive constitutive model descriptions for use in large-scale finite-element simulations of damage and deformation, and (2) focused emphasis on understanding the dynamics of localization phenomena and mechanical failure of polymeric composites.

Duo the energetic characteristic of PBXs, the constitutive models for safety analysis, based on actual physical and chemical mechanisms, to describe complex loading processes must account for complex phenomenology, including temperature, strain rate, orientation effects like cross linking and chain stretching, or texture (created by extrusion or directional formation), and aging effects on mechanical performance.

The macroscopic mechanical properties of PBXs reflect as following: (1) different yield strengths in tension and compression, with the initial yield stress in compression being a factor of 10 or more higher than the initial yield stress in tension(see Pic.1); (2) softening behavior in tension as opposed to initial hardening followed by softening in compression; (3) different degradation of the elastic stiffness in tension and compression; (4) rate sensitivity, especially an increase in the peak strength with strain rate; increasing the strain-rate strongly affects the mechanical response of polymers in tension and compression. Increasing the strain rate leads to higher moduli because the polymer chains have reduced relaxation time; (5) Increasing the hydrostatic pressure leads to higher strength and

ductility(see Pic.2). Under low confining pressures, PBX behaves in a brittle manner; the main failure mechanisms are cracking in tension and crushing in compression. The brittle behavior of PBX disappears when the confining pressure is sufficiently large to prevent crack propagation. In these circumstances failure is driven by the consolidation and collapse of the micro-porous, leading to a macroscopic response that resembles that of a ductile material with work hardening. Modeling the behavior of PBX under large hydrostatic pressures is out of the scope of the plastic-damage model considered here. The constitutive theory in this section aims to capture the effects of irreversible damage associated with the failure mechanisms that occur in PBX materials under fairly low confining pressures (less than four or five times the ultimate compressive stress in uniaxial compression loading).

Pic.1. Stress- plastic strain of PBX 9501 in compression and tension Pic.2. Strength of PBX at various confining pressures

In order to reveal the deformation characteristics of PBX under complex stress states and various strain rates, the material constitutive model is employed in this study based on the damaged plasticity model proposed by Lee and Fenves. The model, which is derived from a generalization of classical plasticity theory and isotropic damage theory of Kachanov, couples plasticity and damage, and is thermodynamically consistent. The yield condition uses the yield function proposed by Lubliner et al. and incorporates the modifications proposed by Lee and Fenves to account for different evolution of strength under tension and compression. The flow potential function is the Drucker-Prager hyperbolic function, and the non-associated potential flow is also assumed. The damage variable, defined as a scalar degradation of material stiffness, is computed from two independent uniaxial damage variables, and weighted by functions of the stress state. For the complex stress state and complex loading path, the scalar degradation variable is consistent with the uniaxial monotonic responses, and captures the complexity associated with the degradation mechanisms. The Steven impact test on PBX is simulated by use of the plastic-damage model, and the ignition threshold for PBX under low velocity impact is discussed

2 THERMODYNAMIC BASIS

The constitutive model proposed is based on the hypothesis of uncoupled elasticity^[1,2]. According to this hypothesis, the total free energy density per unit volume Ψ can be supposed to be formed by two independent parts: an elastic part Ψ^e and a plastic part Ψ^p , corresponding to the elastic and plastic processes respectively,

$$\Psi(\varepsilon_{ij}^e, \kappa^p, d) = \Psi^e(\varepsilon_{ij}^e, d) + \Psi^p(\kappa^p) \quad (1)$$

Where ε_{ij}^e is the elastic strains tensor, κ^p is the plastic hardening variable and d is the damage variable. For small strains and thermally stable problems, the elastic part of free energy density is written as quadratic function as follows,

$$\Psi^e(\varepsilon_{ij}^e, d) = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{ij}^e C_{ijkl}(d) \varepsilon_{kl}^e = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{ij}^e (1-d) C_{ijkl}^0 \varepsilon_{kl}^e = (1-d) \Psi^0 \quad (2)$$

where $C_{ijkl}(d) = (1-d)C_{ijkl}^0$ is the secant constitutive tensor affected by the evolution of damage, C_{ijkl}^0 is the elastic constitutive tensor of the virgin material and $\Psi^0 = \varepsilon_{ij}^e C_{ijkl}^0 \varepsilon_{kl}^e / 2$ represents the elastic free energy density for the virgin material. The damage variable d varies from 0, for the undamaged virgin material, to a maximum value 1 (or ≤ 1), for the completely damaged material, i.e. $0 \leq d \leq 1$.

The fulfillment of inequality of Clausius-Planck for a given thermodynamic state is guaranteed if the stress is obtained as follows,

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{\partial \Psi^e}{\partial \varepsilon_{ij}^e} = (1-d) \frac{\partial \Psi^0}{\partial \varepsilon_{ij}^e} = C_{ijkl}(d) \varepsilon_{kl}^e = (1-d) C_{ijkl}^0 \varepsilon_{kl}^e \quad (3)$$

where σ_{ij} is the stress tensor. Mechanical dissipation must satisfy first inequality of Clausius-Planck and can be

decomposed in two parts: one part due to the plastic process Ξ_m^p and the other due to the damage process Ξ_m^d ,

$$\Xi_m = \sigma_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^p - \frac{\partial \Psi^p}{\partial \kappa^p} \dot{\kappa}^p - \frac{\partial \Psi^e}{\partial d} \dot{d} \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

Where $\epsilon_{ij}^p = \epsilon_{ij} - \epsilon_{ij}^e$ is the plastic strain tensor and ϵ_{ij} is the strain tensor.

3 CONSTITUTIVE RELATIONSHIPS

In the incremental theory of plasticity, the strain tensor, ϵ , is decomposed into the elastic part, ϵ^e , and the plastic part, ϵ^p , which for linear elasticity is given by

$$\epsilon = \epsilon^e + \epsilon^p \quad (5)$$

and

$$\epsilon^e = \mathbf{E}^{-1} : \sigma \quad (6)$$

where the elastic stiffness \mathbf{E} is a rank-four tensor, and σ is the stress tensor. Since the effective stress $\bar{\sigma}$ is defined with the undamaged elastic stiffness from equation (1), it becomes

$$\bar{\sigma} = \mathbf{E}_0 : (\epsilon - \epsilon^p) \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{E}_0 is the initial elastic stiffness tensor. Scalar degradation damage, such that $\mathbf{E} = (1-d)\mathbf{E}_0$, is assumed in many cases. Accordingly, the stress is factorized into stiffness degradation and effective stress parts:

$$\sigma = (1-d)\bar{\sigma} = (1-d)\mathbf{E}_0 : (\epsilon - \epsilon^p) \quad (8)$$

The plastic strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}^p$ is evaluated by the flow rule, which is defined by a scalar plastic potential function Φ . For a plastic potential in the effective stress space, the plastic strain is given by

$$\dot{\epsilon}^p = \dot{\lambda} \nabla_{\bar{\sigma}} \Phi(\bar{\sigma}) = \dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial \Phi(\bar{\sigma})}{\partial \bar{\sigma}} \quad (9)$$

where $\dot{\lambda}$ is a non-negative function referred to as the plastic consistency parameter. In contrast with metals, a non-associative flow rule is necessary to obtain the proper dilatancy exhibited by frictional materials^[3](1988). A Drucker-Prager hyperbolic function is used as the plastic potential function:

$$\Phi = \sqrt{(\epsilon \sigma_{10} \tan \psi)^2 + \bar{q}^2} - \bar{p} \tan \psi \quad (10)$$

Where $\bar{p} = -(1/3)\bar{\sigma} : \mathbf{I}$ is the effective hydrostatic pressure, $\bar{q} = \sqrt{(3/2)\bar{\mathbf{S}} : \bar{\mathbf{S}}}$ is the von Mises equivalent effective stress, $\bar{\mathbf{S}}$ means the deviatoric effective stress, ψ is the dilation angle measured in the p - q plane at high confining pressure; σ_{10} is the uniaxial tensile stress at failure; and ϵ is a parameter, referred to as the eccentricity, that defines the rate at which the function approaches the asymptote (the flow potential tends to a straight line as the eccentricity tends to zero). This flow potential, which is continuous and smooth, ensures that the flow direction is defined uniquely. The function asymptotically approaches the linear Drucker-Prager flow potential at high confining pressure stress and intersects the hydrostatic pressure axis at 90°.

The plastic strain rate is obtained from the flow rule and plastic potential function:

$$\dot{\epsilon}^p = \dot{\lambda} \nabla_{\bar{\sigma}} \Phi(\bar{\sigma}) = \dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial \Phi(\bar{\sigma})}{\partial \bar{\sigma}} \quad (11)$$

Another internal variable set, besides the plastic strain, is needed to represent the damage states. The damage variable, κ , is assumed to be the only necessary state variable and its evolution is expressed as

$$\dot{\kappa} = \dot{\lambda} \mathbf{H}(\bar{\sigma}, \kappa) \quad (12)$$

If the eigenvalues of the plastic strain rate tensor ($\hat{\epsilon}_i$, $i=1,2,3$) are ordered such that $\hat{\epsilon}_{\max}^p = \hat{\epsilon}_1 \geq \hat{\epsilon}_2 \geq \hat{\epsilon}_3 = \hat{\epsilon}_{\min}^p$, the evolution equation for general multiaxial stress conditions can be expressed in the following matrix form:

$$\dot{\hat{\epsilon}}^p = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\hat{\epsilon}}_1^p \\ \dot{\hat{\epsilon}}_2^p \\ \dot{\hat{\epsilon}}_3^p \end{bmatrix} = \hat{\mathbf{h}}(\bar{\sigma}, \tilde{\epsilon}^p) \cdot \hat{\epsilon}^p \quad (13)$$

where

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}(\bar{\sigma}, \tilde{\epsilon}^p) = \begin{bmatrix} r(\bar{\sigma}) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -[1-r(\bar{\sigma})] \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{\epsilon}^p = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\epsilon}_1 \\ \hat{\epsilon}_2 \\ \hat{\epsilon}_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

For the yield surface $F(\bar{\sigma}, \tilde{\epsilon}^p)$, the model makes use of the yield function of Lubliner et. al. ^[4] (1989), with the modifications proposed by Lee and Fenves^[5](1998) to account for different evolution of strength under tension and

compression. The evolution of the yield surface is controlled by the hardening variables, $\tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p$ and $\tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p$. In terms of effective stresses, the yield function takes the form

$$F(\bar{\sigma}, \tilde{\varepsilon}^p) = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} [\bar{q} - 3\alpha\bar{p} + \beta(\tilde{\varepsilon}^p)(\hat{\sigma}_{\max}) - \gamma(-\hat{\sigma}_{\max})] - \bar{\sigma}_c(\tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p) = 0 \quad (14)$$

where α , β and γ are dimensionless material constants taking as $\alpha = \frac{(\sigma_{b0}/\sigma_{c0})-1}{2(\sigma_{b0}/\sigma_{c0})-1}$, $0 \leq \alpha \leq 0.5$, $\beta = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_c(\tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p)}{\bar{\sigma}_t(\tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p)}(1-\alpha) - (1+\alpha)$ and $\gamma = \frac{3(1-K_c)}{2K_c-1}$. $\hat{\sigma}_{\max}$ is the maximum principal effective stress (the algebraically maximum eigenvalue of $\bar{\sigma}$); $(\sigma_{b0}/\sigma_{c0})$ is the ratio of initial equibiaxial compressive yield stress to initial uniaxial compressive yield stress. Typical experimental values of the ratio σ_{b0}/σ_{c0} for PBX are in the range from 1.10 to 1.16, yielding values of α between 0.08 and 0.12. $K_c = q_{TM}/q_{CM}$ is the ratio of the second stress invariant on the tensile meridian, q_{TM} , to that on the compressive meridian, q_{CM} , at initial yield for any given value of the pressure invariant p such that the maximum principal stress is negative, $\hat{\sigma}_{\max} < 0$; it must satisfy the condition $0.5 < K_c \leq 1.0$ (the default value of K_c is $2/3$, i.e. $\gamma \approx 3.0$); $\bar{\sigma}_t(\tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p)$ and $\bar{\sigma}_c(\tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p)$ are the effective tensile and compressive cohesion stresses respectively. The yield function $F(\bar{\sigma}, \tilde{\varepsilon}^p)$ is an extension of the linear Drucker-Prager criterion. While using a friction angle φ , it follows as:

$$F(\bar{\sigma}, \tilde{\varepsilon}^p) = [\bar{q} - \bar{p} \tan \varphi + \beta(\hat{\sigma}_{\max}) - \gamma(-\hat{\sigma}_{\max})] - \left(1 - \frac{\tan \varphi}{3}\right) \bar{\sigma}_c \quad (15)$$

The friction angle is determined from several triaxial compression tests (quasi-static), performed at different confining pressures. A value of 20° agrees well with pressures between 40 and 230 MPa. At zero pressure, an initial yield stress of 5 MPa is considered. Strength loss is reached at a tensile pressure of about -13 MPa.

4 EVOLUTION OF DAMAGE

The model is a continuum, plasticity-based, damage model for PBX assumes that the main two failure mechanisms are tensile cracking and compressive crushing of the concrete material. The evolution of the yield (or failure) surface is controlled by two hardening variables, $\tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p$ and $\tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p$, linked to failure mechanisms under tension and compression loading, respectively. We refer to $\tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p$ and $\tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p$ as tensile and compressive equivalent plastic strains, respectively.

Under uniaxial tension the stress-strain response follows a linear elastic relationship until the value of the failure stress, σ_{0t} , is reached. The failure stress corresponds to the onset of micro-cracking in the concrete material. Beyond the failure stress the formation of micro-cracks is represented macroscopically with a softening stress-strain response, which induces strain localization in the concrete structure.

Under uniaxial compression the response is linear until the value of initial yield, σ_{c0} . In the plastic regime the response is typically characterized by stress hardening followed by strain softening beyond the ultimate stress, σ_{cu} . This representation, although somewhat simplified, captures the main features of the response of concrete.

It is assumed that the uniaxial stress-strain curves can be converted into stress versus plastic-strain curves. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_t &= \sigma_t(\tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p, \dot{\tilde{\varepsilon}}_t^p, \theta, f_i) \\ \sigma_c &= \sigma_c(\tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p, \dot{\tilde{\varepsilon}}_c^p, \theta, f_i) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where the subscripts t and c refer to tension and compression, respectively; $\tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p$ and $\tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p$ are the equivalent plastic strains, $\dot{\tilde{\varepsilon}}_t^p$ and $\dot{\tilde{\varepsilon}}_c^p$ are the equivalent plastic strain rates, θ is the temperature, and f_i , ($i=1,2,\dots$) are other predefined field variables.

When the PBX specimen is unloaded from any point on the strain softening branch of the stress-strain curves, the unloading response is weakened: the elastic stiffness of the material appears to be damaged (or degraded). The degradation of the elastic stiffness is characterized by two damage variables, d_t and d_c , which are assumed to be functions of the plastic strains, temperature, and field variables:

$$\begin{aligned} d_t &= d_t(\tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p, \theta, f_i); \quad 0 \leq d_t \leq 1 \\ d_c &= d_c(\tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p, \theta, f_i); \quad 0 \leq d_c \leq 1 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The damage variables can take values from zero, representing the undamaged material, to one, which represents total loss of strength.

If E_0 is the initial (undamaged) elastic stiffness of the material, the stress-strain relations under uniaxial tension and compression loading are, respectively:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_t &= (1 - d_t)E_0(\varepsilon_t - \tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p) \\ \sigma_c &= (1 - d_c)E_0(\varepsilon_c - \tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p)\end{aligned}\quad (18)$$

We define the “effective” tensile and compressive cohesion stresses as

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\sigma}_t &= \frac{\sigma_t}{1 - d_t} = E_0(\varepsilon_t - \tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p) \\ \bar{\sigma}_c &= \frac{\sigma_c}{1 - d_c} = E_0(\varepsilon_c - \tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p)\end{aligned}\quad (19)$$

The effective cohesion stresses determine the size of the yield (or failure) surface.

The evolution equations for the hardening variables must be extended for the general multiaxial conditions. Based on Lee and Fenves (1998) we assume that the equivalent plastic strain rates are evaluated according to the expressions:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\tilde{\varepsilon}}_t^p &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} r(\boldsymbol{\sigma})\hat{\varepsilon}_{\max}^p \\ d\tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} r(\boldsymbol{\sigma})d\varepsilon_{\max}^p \\ \dot{\tilde{\varepsilon}}_c^p &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} -[1 - r(\boldsymbol{\sigma})]\hat{\varepsilon}_{\min}^p \\ d\tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} -[1 - r(\boldsymbol{\sigma})]d\varepsilon_{\min}^p\end{aligned}\quad (20)$$

Where $\hat{\varepsilon}_{\max}^p$ and $\hat{\varepsilon}_{\min}^p$ are, respectively, the maximum and minimum eigenvalues of the plastic strain rate tensor $\dot{\varepsilon}^p$. $r(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}})$ is a multiaxial stress weight factor, defined as

$$r(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 \langle \hat{\sigma}_i \rangle}{\sum_{i=1}^3 |\hat{\sigma}_i|} = \frac{\langle \hat{\sigma}_1 \rangle + \langle \hat{\sigma}_2 \rangle + \langle \hat{\sigma}_3 \rangle}{|\hat{\sigma}_1| + |\hat{\sigma}_2| + |\hat{\sigma}_3|}; \quad 0 \leq r(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}) \leq 1 \quad (21)$$

$$r(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{\hat{\sigma}_1 + \hat{\sigma}_2 + \hat{\sigma}_3}{|\hat{\sigma}_1| + |\hat{\sigma}_2| + |\hat{\sigma}_3|} \right) \quad (22)$$

where $\hat{\sigma}_i$ ($i=1,2,\dots$) are the principal stress components. The Macauley bracket $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is defined by $\langle x \rangle = \frac{1}{2}(|x| + x)$. $r(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}})$ is equal to one if all principal stresses $\hat{\sigma}_i$ ($i=1,2,3$) are positive and equal to zero if they are negative.

$$1 - d = (1 - s_t d_c)(1 - s_c d_t) \quad (23)$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned}s_t &= 1 - w_t r^*(\boldsymbol{\sigma}); \quad 0 \leq w_t \leq 1 \\ s_c &= 1 - w_c (1 - r^*(\boldsymbol{\sigma})); \quad 0 \leq w_c \leq 1\end{aligned}\quad (24)$$

That is

$$1 - d = \{1 - [1 - w_t r^*(\boldsymbol{\sigma})]d_c\} \{1 - [1 - w_c (1 - r^*(\boldsymbol{\sigma}))]d_t\} \quad (25)$$

5 STRAIN RATE AND TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE

Using testing data from quasi-static triax tests^[6], Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) and modest rate uniaxial compression tests^[7,8], the strain rate dependence of peak stress can be described as following functional R ,

$$R = \left(1 + \frac{\dot{\varepsilon}^p}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0 \exp[\alpha(T - T_0)]} \right)^{ep} \quad (26)$$

where $\dot{\varepsilon}_0$ is 5.6 s^{-1} , α is 0.184 and ep is 0.14.

6. EXPERIMENTAL TEST VEHICLES, RESULTS AND SIMULATION

The AWE Steven test comprises of a 70 mm diameter by 12.7 mm thick explosive disc with a 10 mm (radial) thick PTFE ring surrounding it. These are located inside a steel base unit, which provides a high level of confinement both radially and to the rear of the explosive. A 3 mm thick steel cover plate is located on top of the target providing full confinement to the explosive sample. The cover plate is secured to the base unit by a steel

strong ring which bolts to the target stand plate. A 1.6 kg round nosed 50 mm diameter cylindrical steel projectile is fired at the centre of the cover plate of the target vehicle from a gas gun, Figure 3. The impact velocity of the projectile is varied in order to determine the threshold for reaction of the explosive being tested^[9].

The impact reaction threshold speed for the HMX-based explosive under consideration is between 62 and 64 m/s when impacted by the round nosed projectile in the AWE Steven test. Impacts at speeds lower than the threshold value leave dents in the cover plate, Figures 4. The calculation results with nominal values after the projectile begins to rebound are shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 3. Schematic of AWE Steven Test vehicle and projectile

The ignition problem of PBXs under low velocity impact has been a challenge in the field of impact dynamics and energetic material science. It's a coupled mechanical- thermal-chemical complex process. Establishment of ignition criterion for PBXs under low velocity impact is a dream for engineers and scientific researchers. Gruau adopt a criterion to analyze ignition of a confined high explosive under low velocity, which is based on the work of Browning and Scammon^[10], which integrates the history of pressure and plastic shear rate, for varying flux conditions:

$$D_{ig} = \frac{1}{c_*} \int_0^{t_{ig}} \left(\frac{t_{ig} - \tau}{t_*} \right)^{-n} \left(\frac{\langle p(\tau) \rangle}{p_*} \right)^{2n/3} \dot{\gamma}^p(\tau) d\tau = 1 \quad (27)$$

where c_* is the threshold value, t_* is a characteristic time, p_* is a characteristic pressure, $\langle p(\tau) \rangle$ is the positive part of the pressure and the exponent n comes from the HMX decomposition kinetics. When(27) is met, ignition is supposed to occur. In this work, the Reaugh criterion^[11] is used for ignition prediction. The criterion, which is established based on the observation that in low-speed impacts, ignition is accompanied by significant shear deformation, is a pure mechanical condition, easily used in hydrocode. The Reaugh criterion parameter uses shear weighting factor $f_\tau = 2 - 27 |J_3| / 2Y$, which depends on the third invariant J_3 and flow stress Y , and contains a weighting factor for the normal stress acting on the plane of maximum shear. When the normal stress is tensile, the weight is zero. This term was motivated by the view that more frictional work is done on an interface when the normal stress is more compressive. The ignition parameter is given by

$$D_{ig}(t) = \int_0^t \left(2 - \frac{27 |J_3|}{2Y^3} \right)^5 \left(\frac{p + s_2 / 2}{\sigma_0} \right)^{1/2} \dot{\epsilon}^p d\tau = 1 \quad (28)$$

Here σ_0 is a parameter of order 50 MPa.

Use of this criterion in simulations of the US and UK variants of the Steven test^[12] have shown that ignition in both tests occurs when D_{ig} reaches 200, although the peak pressures in the two tests differ by nearly a factor of 2. Similarly, scorch marks on the steel holder from UK tests are not on the axis of symmetry, where the pressure is largest, but at an intermediate radius, near where the criterion has its maximum value.

Computer simulations of Steven tests have shown that the value of the ignition criterion is quite sensitive to the coefficient of friction used^[12,13](Reaugh,2010,2011).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Financial supports provided by the National Natural Science Foundation of China under Grant Number 11472257, and the fund of CAEP-SCNS under contracts R2014-0401-25 and R2015-0401-15 are gratefully acknowledged. In addition, the authors would like to thank the CAEP-SCNS Engineering mechanics team for providing extensive support and validation assistance with the code PANDA-Impact.

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